

EXTRUSION OF AA6061 ALUMINUM ALLOYS REINFORCED WITH
CERAMIC SHORT FIBERS

K.Suganuma, K.Niihara and T.Fujita
(National Defense Academy, Hashirimizu 1-10-20,
Yokosuka, Kanagawa 239, Japan)
N.Suzuki
(A.M.Technology Co.,Ltd., Matsunaga 622-1, Numazu,
Shizuoka 410, Japan)

ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties and interfacial microstructures between fibers and the matrix of AA6061 aluminum alloys reinforced with alumina short fiber and with potassium titanate whisker were examined. The extruded composite with potassium titanate whisker had a good strength beyond 410 MPa. Reaction at the interface was not serious. The strength of the composites increased by raising extrusion temperature and the highest strength was achieved by a semisolid extrusion process using a cladding with pure aluminum, by which damage of ceramic fibers was remarkably reduced and surface tearing was suppressed. The reaction between fiber and matrix, however, must be prevented by shortening the heating duration. For both fibers, magnesium in the matrix is the most reactive alloying element. It was possible to achieve very high aspect ratio beyond 30 even after extrusion, which enabled to strengthen the composites effectively.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloy matrix composites reinforced with ceramic fibers, which are called shortly as FRMs in the present paper, are expected to have favorable properties such as light weight, high strength, high modulus, and resistance to wear. Although there are several establishments of those FRMs, the utilizations are limited within narrow special applications such as aerospace and military ones, for which the fabrication cost of FRMs may not restrict their utilizations. In order to expand the utilization of FRMs to the wide commercial products such as automobile engine parts, the establishment of the fabrication processes of low cost but high quality FRMs are earnestly required.

The FRMs with short fibers such as potassium titanate whisker and alumina short fiber may be the most cost saving in fabrication because both of the possibility of mass-production by adoption of the squeeze casting and of the low costs of the fibers themselves. Because potassium titanate whisker has no competitive fiber in cost, it would be the best if enough reinforcement of alloys could be achieved. However, recent works reported that reaction between the whisker and aluminum matrices has been a serious problem^{1,2}. One of the aims of the present paper is to examine the reaction using a newly developed potassium titanate whisker and the possibility of utilization of it as the reinforcement of aluminum.

The second subject is the examination of extrusion processes of those FRMs. In order to obtain strong FRMs, the ceramic fibers are required to be longer (or to have large aspect ratio) and to be aligned unidirectionally. Because as-cast FRMs have fibers in random direction, secondary fabrication processes such as extrusion, rolling and forging at high temperature, are required for the alignment of the fibers. Several works on these secondary fabrications have been reported recently³⁻⁷. However, ceramic fibers usually become far shorter than the critical length of the fibers chopped up during these secondary fabrication processes⁴. These "short" fiber-reinforced composites only have been used for the abrasive purposes. The second aim

was, therefore, to improve the present status of the hot-extrusion process by applying a semisolid process and to make problems in such a process clearer.

EXPERIMENTAL

Starting materials were supplied as rods of as-cast AA6061 alloy matrix FRMs reinforced with 15 vol% alumina short fiber or with 20 vol% potassium titanate whiskers. The alumina fibers containing 15 wt% silica was supplied by Denka Co.,Ltd.(DENKA ALCEN). The average length and diameter of the fibers were 100 μm and 3 μm , respectively. The potassium whisker ($\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{TiO}_2$) was supplied by Titan Kogyo Co.,Ltd.(HT-300). The length and the diameter were in the ranges of 10 - 100 μm and of 0.4 - 1.5 μm , respectively. The FRMs were fabricated by a squeeze cast in which the temperatures of the preforms, the melt and the mold were 1073 K, 1073 K and 523 K, respectively and the pressure was 230 MPa. The fibers were in random direction. The diameter of the FRM rod was 36 mm. Billets of 30 mm in length were cut from the rods.

The details of extrusion process was reported in ref.8. Pure aluminum was selected as the cladding layer for the FRM. The disk of aluminum of 10 mm in thickness was placed in front of the billet. The extrusion ratio was 19. Before extrusion, the FRMs were held at the extrusion temperature for 20 min. Only for the semisolid extrusion, the extrusion was started just after the temperature inside the billet reached the extrusion temperature to prevent reaction between the fibers and the matrix. The extrusion speed was 1.2 mm/sec.

The tensile specimen of which the cross section of the parallel part was 4 mm x 1.5 mm were cut from the extruded rod. All specimens were T6 heat-treated (solution-treated at 793K for 30 min - water quench - aged at 348 K for 8h). A part of the tensile specimens extruded at 723 K were heat-treated before T6 treatment at various conditions simulating the high temperature extrusion heat cycle. A tensile test was carried out at a strain rate of 1.4×10^{-3} /sec.

Distribution of fibers before and after extrusion were examined by extracting fibers from the matrix with a solution of 75% hydrochloric acid and 25% nitric acid. About 300 fibers were measured for each FRM. Scanning electron microscopy(SEM) and transmission electron microscopy(TEM) were carried out on the as-cast and heat-treated specimens to examine the interfacial reaction. The specimen for TEM was made by argon ion thinning after electropolishing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Availability of potassium titanate whisker as the reinforcement

Figure 1 summarizes tensile strength, Young's modulus and thermal expansion coefficient of the present composite along the extrusion axis compared with AA6061 alloys without any reinforcement and with 15 vol% alumina short fiber. All were extruded at 773 K and T6 treated. It is apparent that the composite with potassium

Fig.1 Comparison of tensile strength (σ_T), Young's modulus(E) and thermal expansion coefficient(α) among AA6061 alloys without any reinforcements(MA), with 15 vol% alumina short fiber(CA), and with 20 vol% potassium titanate whisker(CK). All were extruded at 773 K and T6 treated.

titanate whisker exhibits a quite good strength beyond 410 MPa and high Young's modulus compared with the composite with alumina fiber even considering the volume fraction being slightly larger.

Figure 2 shows the TEM image and the energy dispersive analysis across the interface of the T6 treated composite. Little precipitate was observed on the whisker/matrix interface. Furthermore, potassium was not detected in the matrix, which had been one of the serious problems for this system. However, slight enrichment of magnesium was recognized on the interface. This enrichment was also recognized in the as-cast composite. Figure 3 shows the high resolution TEM image of the whisker/matrix interface. Very narrow reaction layer below 10 nm was recognized along the interface.

Fig.2 TEM image and EDX profiles taken from the points A:in the whisker, B:on the interface, and C:in the matrix. "F" indicates whiskers.

Fig.3 High resolution image of the whisker/matrix interface. The thickness of the reaction layer is below 10 nm. Lattice fringes from small precipitates are recognized.

The enrichment of magnesium on the fiber/matrix interface is always recognized in the ceramic fiber/AA6061 alloy system because magnesium is one of the most active elements against most ceramics. The segregation of magnesium at the interface must be avoided because the depletion of magnesium from the matrix causes the weakening of the matrix as shown in the next section. This requires the optimization of processing parameters of the squeeze casting. The lower temperature is better but it must be high enough to get complete infiltration. The parameters in the present work, especially the temperature, were not optimum. The lower temperature of the preform and the melt, for example, 973 K, could be adopted if the mold temperature would be raised. In such a case, the enrichment of magnesium would decrease. However, it could be concluded that, even though there is some reaction between potassium titanate whisker and magnesium, the composite can have good properties as shown in Fig.1 and, therefore, that the potassium titanate whisker can be one of the most beneficial fibers as the reinforcement of aluminum alloys by commercial productions.

2. Influence of High Temperature Exposure of FRM

Figure 4 shows the dependences of the fracture strength on the exposure temperature and time. The fracture strength decreased gradually with increased exposure temperature. Exposed for only 10 min at 873 K, the specimen dropped by 10 % in strength from that of the as-extruded specimen (T6-treated). The strength also decreased with increasing exposure time. After 5 h exposure a 40 % drop in strength occurred.

Fig.4 Influence of high temperature exposure on fracture stress of the FRM with alumina short fiber extruded at 723 K. (A)Exposure temperature. (B)Exposure time.

The TEM photograph of the interface between the alumina fiber and the matrix of the FRM exposed at 723 K for 5 h is shown in Fig.5. Magnesium also segregated at the fiber/matrix interface. The reaction products were recognized at the interface. From the electron diffraction pattern, the precipitate was determined to be a spinel $MgAl_2O_4$. Thus, magnesium precipitated on the surface of alumina fibers.

It is possible to deduce that the degradation in strength by high temperature exposure was caused by decreasing magnesium in the matrix because the precipitation hardening of Mg_2Si cannot be expected. In addition to this effect, weakening of fibers by sharp stress concentration around precipitates will be also one of the reason. Thus, because the strength of the FRM decreased with increasing exposure temperature or time, the extrusion must be carried out at lower temperature or within shorter time.

Fig.5 TEM image of the interface between alumina fiber and matrix of the FRM exposed to 853 K for 5 h.

3. Effect of Extrusion Temperature on Properties of FRM

In order to prevent the damage of fibers during extrusion, raising extrusion temperature is effective because the flow stress is reduced. Although the semisolid extrusion seems to be better, above the solidus temperature, surface tearing becomes

Fig.6 Comparison of surface appearances of extruded FRM.

severe because of very weak bonding of matrix in semisolid-state as shown in Fig.6(A). This is one of the most serious problems in a semisolid extrusion. In order to prevent this phenomenon, the clad process with a pure aluminum surface layer was adopted. Figure 6(B) shows the rod extruded at 883 K by cladding. The surface was very smooth with no tearing in spite of the higher temperature than that shown in Fig.6(A). Thus, the clad extrusion effectively prevented surface tearing in a semisolid extrusion.

Figure 7 summarizes the change in average fiber length as a function of extrusion temperature. The length of the fiber of the FRM extruded below about 850 K was about 20 μm and did not change remarkably. The aspect ratio of the fiber was about 5 - 8. Below the aspect ratio of 10, we could not expect effective reinforcement mechanism¹⁰. The length increased drastically by a semisolid extrusion and it reached 90 μm , the aspect ratio of which was beyond 30. This value has not been obtained by the other extrusion processes. The tensile strength of the FRM increased by raising the extrusion temperature in agreement with the change in fiber length as also shown in Fig.7. Thus, the semisolid extrusion process with cladding is proved to be very much effective to produce a strong FRM by reducing a damage of fiber reinforcements.

As pointed in the previous section, higher temperature secondary fabrications might cause degradation of FRMs by a severe reaction at fiber/matrix interfaces. For the alumina/AA6061 alloy system, the strength decreased 10% by the heat treatment even at 873 K for 10 min. However, it is possible to minimize by setting treatment time as short as possible. In the present case the reaction was effectively suppressed by shortening the holding time before extrusion.

Fig.7 Changes in average length of alumina fiber(A) and in tensile strength at room temperature(B) as a function of extrusion temperature.

CONCLUSION

In the present paper, the mechanical properties and the fiber/matrix interfacial reactions of the AA6061 alloys reinforced with potassium titanate whisker and with alumina short fiber were examined.

Potassium titanate whisker was proved to be one of the best candidates for the reinforcements of aluminum. It does not react severely with aluminum. The extruded FRM exhibited a good strength.

The strength of the extruded FRM increased by raising extrusion temperature and the highest strength was achieved by a semisolid extrusion process, by which damage of fibers was remarkably prevented. A simple semisolid-state extrusion, however, caused severe tears on the surface of an extruded rod. To suppress tearing, an FRM was clothed with the layer of pure aluminum which was in a solid-state at the extrusion temperature. By this method, a semisolid extrusion could be performed without tearing. The highest aspect ratio of the fiber after semisolid extrusion reached 30, which is enough to strengthen the FRM.

A high temperature heat treatment of FRMs sometimes causes severe reaction at the fiber/matrix interface, which degrades the mechanical properties of the FRMs. In the present two composites, magnesium was the main reactive element. By cutting holding time at elevated temperature as short as possible, the reaction was suppressed effectively. Finally, we can get the second conclusion that the semisolid extrusion process using a cladding method has advantages of producing a strong FRM by preventing fibers from chopping during extrusion.

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